

Welcome to our joint newsletter! Get ready for the latest updates and insights from Climate Farm Demo and ClimateSmartAdvisors.

750 DYNAMIC DEMO EVENTS IN 2024

In the upcoming year, we're gearing up for an impressive 750 demonstration events, where 50% of demo farms will play host. But what exactly is a demo event? These on-farm showcases spotlight innovations in real farm settings, offering hands-on experiences and practical insights into farming methods and technologies. These authentic learning opportunities empower participants to directly enhance their own farming practices. Beyond knowledge exchange, demo events serve as valuable networking opportunities, creating meeting points for all participants. Get ready for an exciting year ahead filled with enriching events!

LEARN MORE

It was a pleasure to kick-off the series of demo-events in Finland with such an active and diverse group of farmers involved. Our first demo event focused on biogas production which triggered interesting discussions of the multiple pathways for implementing different scales of climate smart solutions on farms.

Maria Suomela
ProAgria

1,250 PILOT DEMO FARMS RECRUITED

We are thrilled to announce the remarkable progress in Climate Farm Demo, with a total of **1,250 pilot demonstration farms** recruited and registered across **26 countries**. The diversity of these farms is impressive, showcasing the broad spectrum of agricultural systems engaged in our project. Among them, **64.6% (805)** are dedicated to **animal husbandry and mixed farming systems**, **18.2% (228)** focus on **horticulture crops**, **17.5% (219)** represent **specialized arable crops farms**, and **26.1% (326)** proudly stand as **organic farms**. This widespread participation reflects the robust commitment and enthusiasm of our farming communities toward adopting climate-smart practices.

GREENHOUSE GAS FARM AUDIT

Embarking on a transformative journey until **March 2024**, the Climate Farm Demo project is laying the foundation for the **Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP)** of each pilot demonstration farm. Central to this initiative is the completion of a **Greenhouse Gas (GHG) farm audit**, establishing emissions profiles for each farmer, and supporting the adoption of tailored adaptation and mitigation measures (AMMs). The AMP serves as a comprehensive document outlining each farm's pathway to enhance its climate-related environmental performance, with ongoing collaboration between farmers and the project team.

For additional details, refer to milestone MSTI Guidelines and Training Module for AMM Advise Ready. If you don't have access, reach out to your NCs.

TRAINING SESSIONS - FEBRUARY 2024

Gear up for an enriching experience in February 2024 - training sessions dedicated to the implementation of the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan. These sessions will delve into the utilization of Adaptation and Mitigation measures, explore relevant tools, and provide insights into Greenhouse Gas (GHG) accounting.

WEBSITE LAUNCH

Exciting news for our community! The **ClimateSmartAdvisors website** is now live, serving as a central hub for a wealth of valuable information, resources, and innovative tools. Farmers, advisors, and stakeholders can explore the latest insights and practices to navigate the dynamic realm of sustainable agriculture. Explore it and make the most of the extensive information and insights available!

[CLICK HERE](#)

RECRUITMENT OF THE CLIMATE SMART COACHES

We are delighted to announce the recruitment of **40 Climate Smart Coaches** to ClimateSmartAdvisors, aligning with our set goals. Each of the prominent countries—France, Germany, Spain, Italy, Poland, and the UK—has three Climate Smart Coaches, while the remaining 21 medium and lower emission countries have one each. This accomplishment brings us great joy as we contribute to shaping the future of climate-smart farming in Europe!

WWW.CLIMATESMARTADVISORS.EU

INSIGHTS ON CLIMATE SMART ADVISORY CONTEXTS ACROSS THE EU

Deliverable 1.1 aims to provide the overview of the context for climate smart advisory services in all ClimateSmartAdvisors project's partner countries and laying a foundation to develop the CSA network in each of those countries. Through the deliverable we aim to understand the current state-of-play of the conditions and context in which agricultural advisors are currently working in across project countries. For this purpose, a survey was launched in the beginning of the project (September 2023) and was completed by 1104 respondents. To access the survey, kindly contact your National Coordinator.

COUNTRY REPORTS AVAILABLE

Recent survey insights on climate-smart advisory services are out, with **individual country reports now available**. These reports will shape upcoming national kick-off meetings in February and March. But there's more—these reports play a key role in directing national project activities, from CoP themes to focus areas for annual and AKIS meetings. To deepen these insights, we've included reflection questions in the country reports. We urge National Coordinators to address these during the kick-off meetings, providing invaluable perspectives.

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